

National
COVID
Cohort
Collaborative

N3C Query Report: Pre-existing Chronic Conditions

Date: May 12, 2022

PIs: Emily Pfaff, Richard Moffitt, Tell Bennett, Chris Chute, Melissa Haendel

Analysts: Nariman Ammar, Michael Evans, Suchetha Sharma, Margaret Hall, Richard Moffitt, Jason Yoo, Johanna Loomba

Revisions and visuals: Julie McMurry

Abstract

The overall goal is to identify the relative risk of developing PASC for patients with three specific pre-existing chronic conditions. Here, Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA) and Multiple Sclerosis (MS) are each defined by diagnosis codes, while Diabetes Melitus (DM) is defined by a combination of diagnosis codes and Hemoglobin A1c levels. In order to investigate the confounding effect of obesity (OB), we further defined obesity with a combination of diagnosis codes and observed BMI data. These pre-existing conditions showed increased odds ratios for developing PASC. Of the four, OSA had the highest adjusted odds ratio, followed by MS. The odds ratio for DM was small, with obesity having a stronger correlation to PASC than diabetes.

Methods

Inclusion criteria

(see RESULTS for CONSORT diagram)

- **Study period:** 3/1/2020 - 2/28/2022
- **Age:** Any age
- **COVID-19 positive:** via a qualifying index event between 3/1/2020 – 2/28/2022
 - Definition 1. Positive SARS-CoV-2 PCR test (no antibody tests)
 - Definition 2. Diagnosis of COVID-19 via 1 inpatient or 2 outpatient instances of ICD-10 code U07.1
- **Utilization:** Had 2 or more visits within the health system within the two years prior to their COVID-19 index date
- Did not die within 30 days of their COVID-19 index date

(see below for CONSORT diagram)

Data were from release version 72 of the N3C data enclave, released on April 2, 2022. Site-level quality filters were applied prior to analysis in order to remove 13 of the 72 data partners with significant and systematic missingness according to the following criteria: sites (1) should not shift dates by more than 30 days, (2) should have serum creatinine and lymphocyte count results for at least 25% of hospitalizations, and (3) should not have >10% of their hospitalizations where the COVID-19 index date is more than 200 days after the visit start date.

Analysis

The relationships between pre-existing conditions (OSA, MS, DM, OB) present at the time of COVID diagnosis and subsequent development of PASC were examined using logistic regression models, both in univariable models and in multivariable models that included OSA, MS, DM, OB, age, gender, and race/ethnicity as predictors. Age was included as a natural cubic spline term to allow for nonlinearity. Results are reported as odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals.

Definitions

Index event

The earliest instance of COVID-19 positivity via a qualifying index event occurring between 3/1/2020 and end of the study period (2/28/2022). First COVID positivity is defined by either Definition 1 or 2 (test or diagnosis).

Pre-existing conditions

Evidence of a pre-pandemic (3/1/2018 - 3/1/2020) documentation of MS, OSA, or diabetes (via EHR visits) from the computable phenotype definitions below:

Diagnosis of OSA ¹	At least two instances of relevant diagnostic codes on separate days (ICD-10-CM: G47.30, G47.33, G47.39; ICD-9-CM: 327.20, 327.23, 327.29, 780.51, 780.53, 780.57)
Diagnosis of MS ^{2,3}	Three or more encounters (inpatient or outpatient) with a qualifying diagnosis (ICD-10-CM: G35.X) within a year-long period
Diagnosis of diabetes DM) (types 1 and 2) ^{4,5}	Two or more instances of relevant diagnostic codes (ICD-10-CM: E08.X to E13.X) <u>OR</u> Most recent pre-pandemic HbA1c value greater than 6.4 (LOINC: 17856-6, 4548-4, 4549-2. <i>OID</i> : 2.16.840.1.113883.3.464.1003.198.12.1013)

Since BMI is associated with OSA and Diabetes, we also looked into Obesity (OB) as a pre-pandemic existing condition. We included patients who had at least two instances of relevant diagnosis codes for obesity or those who had a BMI greater than or equal to 30.

ICD codes for pre-existing conditions were mapped to OMOP concept ids. The concepts were manually curated, resulting in 14 translations for diabetes being dropped. In total, 126 concepts were used to diagnose diabetes, 2 concepts were used to diagnose OSA, and one concept was used to diagnose MS (see tables below and appendix for code mapping).

OMOP concept ID	Disease	OMOP concept name
374919	MS	Multiple sclerosis

OMOP concept ID	Disease	OMOP concept name
442588	OSA	Obstructive sleep apnea syndrome
313459	OSA	Sleep apnea

Diagnosis of PASC

PASC was defined as previously described⁶, trained on a cohort of patients who were known to have visited a long-COVID specialty clinic. In order to label a patient as having PASC or not, the patient must meet the following criteria: (1) they must be at least 18 years old, (2) they must have at least 2 days of data in the system, (3) they must have at least one diagnosis and one medication in the pre- or post-index period, and (4) they must have data at least 90 days since the covid index.

Cell size and patient privacy protection

In order to comply with N3C data use policies, any cell sizes under 20 were suppressed and the surrounding row and column data were adjusted with small gaussian noise in order to obfuscate the suppressed counts.

Results

An accounting of the patients meeting our inclusion criteria for COVID positivity is shown below. On average patients had 25 visit-days in the study period (Median: 14; Std. Dev: 34.2). Patients' average age was 48.4 years (Median: 48, Std. Dev: 18.7). 137 patients were removed from study for having a death date within 30 days of their index date. A total of 1,570,171 patients were eligible for the study. Of those, a total of 158,425 had PASC and a total of 366,991 had evidence for at least one of the four conditions in the pre pandemic period based on the computable phenotype definitions in the Table above.

Definition 1: Test-positive

Table 1. Number of patients in the study period who developed PASC, by age, race, ethnicity, and sex, and presence of pre-existing chronic conditions

	All COVID+	PASC	Not PASC
Age			
18 to 20	71,199 (5.08)	1,537 (1.11)	69,662 (5.52)
21 to 35	339,579 (24.25)	19,112 (13.85)	320,467 (25.38)
36 to 45	228,110 (16.29)	30,615 (22.18)	197,495 (15.64)
46 to 55	238,964 (17.06)	29,567 (21.42)	209,397 (16.59)
56 to 65	235,385 (16.81)	32,978 (23.9)	202,407 (16.03)
66+	287,243 (20.51)	24,196 (17.53)	263,047 (20.84)
Sex			
Male	549,473 (39.23)	33,356 (24.17)	516,117 (40.88)
Female	850,696 (60.74)	104,608 (75.8)	746,088 (59.10)
Other/Missing/Unknown	311 (0.02)	41 (0.03)	270 (0.02)
Race ethnicity			
White Non-Hispanic	949,341 (67.79)	94,269 (68.31)	855,072 (67.73)
Black or African American Non-Hispanic	181,538 (12.96)	19,028 (13.79)	162,510 (12.87)
Hispanic or Latino Any Race	159,752 (11.41)	14,724 (10.67)	145,028 (11.49)
Asian Non-Hispanic	29,733 (2.12)	2,793 (2.02)	26,940 (2.13)
NHOPI* Non-Hispanic	1,530 (0.11)	137 (0.1)	1,393 (0.11)
Other Non-Hispanic	14,764 (1.05)	1,427 (1.03)	13,337 (1.06)
Unknown	63,822 (4.56)	5,627 (4.08)	58,195 (4.61)
Pre-existing conditions			
OSA	38,623 (2.76)	6,713 (4.86)	31,910 (2.53)
MS	2,129 (0.15)	426 (0.31)	1,703 (0.13)
Diabetes	142,139 (10.15)	16,894 (12.24)	125,245 (9.92)
Obesity	221,201 (15.79)	29,363 (21.28)	191,838 (15.20)
No Diabetes	1,258,341 (89.85)	121,111 (87.76)	1,137,230 (90.08)
No MS	1,398,351 (99.85)	137,579 (99.69)	1,260,772 (99.87)
No Obesity	1,179,279 (84.21)	108,642 (78.72)	1,070,637 (84.80)
No OSA	1,361,857 (97.24)	131,292 (95.14)	1,230,565 (97.47)

* Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander

Table 2. Frequency of pre-existing chronic conditions and their association with risk of developing PASC

Condition		N	N PASC	% PASC	univariate OR	adjusted OR
OSA	Yes	38,623	6,713	17.4%	1.97 (1.92, 2.03)	1.66 (1.61, 1.71)
	No	1,361,857	131,292	9.6%		
MS	Yes	2,129	426	20.0%	2.29 (2.06, 2.55)	1.58 (1.41, 1.75)
	No	1,398,351	137,579	9.8%		
DM	Yes	142,139	16,894	11.9%	1.27 (1.25, 1.29)	1.06 (1.04, 1.08)
	No	1,258,341	121,111	9.6%		
OB	Yes	221,201	29,363	13.3%	1.51 (1.49, 1.53)	1.22 (1.20, 1.23)
	No	1,179,279	108,642	9.2%		

Definition 2: Diagnosis-positive

Table 1. Number of patients in the study period who developed PASC, by age, race, ethnicity, and sex, and presence of pre-existing chronic conditions

	All COVID+	PASC	not PASC
Age			
18 to 20	15,566 (2.81)	728 (1.05)	14,838 (3.06)
21 to 35	96,009 (17.31)	8,657 (12.47)	87,352 (18.00)
36 to 45	76,973 (13.88)	12,185 (17.55)	64,788 (13.35)
46 to 55	91,720 (16.54)	13,807 (19.89)	77,913 (16.06)
56 to 65	107,096 (19.31)	17,433 (25.11)	89,663 (18.48)
66+	167,311 (30.16)	16,604 (23.92)	150,707 (31.06)
Sex			
Male	227,719 (41.05)	20,832 (30.01)	206,915 (42.64)
Female	326,837 (58.92)	48,598 (70.01)	278,241 (57.34)
Other/Missing/Unknown	119 (0.02)	<20	105 (0.02)
Race Ethnicity			
White Non-Hispanic	343,369 (61.9)	44,023 (63.42)	299,346 (61.69)
Black or African American Non-Hispanic	87,857 (15.84)	11,395 (16.42)	76,462 (15.76)
Hispanic or Latino Any Race	75,990 (13.7)	8,853 (12.75)	67,137 (13.84)
Asian Non-Hispanic	14,307 (2.58)	1,709 (2.46)	12,598 (2.60)
NHOPI* Non-Hispanic	761 (0.14)	89 (0.13)	672 (0.14)
Other Non-Hispanic	3,638 (0.66)	503 (0.72)	3,135 (0.65)
Unknown	28,753 (5.18)	2,842 (4.09)	25,911 (5.34)
Pre-existing Conditions			
OSA	27,653 (4.99)	5,630 (8.11)	22,023 (4.54)
MS	1,647 (0.3)	365 (0.53)	1,282 (0.26)
Diabetes	88,362 (15.93)	12,517 (18.03)	75,845 (15.63)
Obesity	139,799 (25.2)	22,619 (32.59)	117,180 (24.15)
No Diabetes	466,313 (84.07)	56,897 (81.97)	409,416 (84.37)
No MS	553,028 (99.7)	69,049 (99.47)	483,979 (99.74)
No Obesity	414,876 (74.8)	46,795 (67.41)	368,081 (75.85)
No OSA	527,022 (95.01)	63,784 (91.89)	463,238 (95.46)

* Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander

Table 2. Frequency of pre-existing chronic conditions and their association with risk of developing PASC

Condition	N	N PASC	% PASC	univariate OR	adjusted OR	
OSA	Yes	27,653	5,630	20.4%	1.86 (1.80, 1.91)	1.59 (1.53, 1.64)
	No	527,022	63,784	12.1%		
MS	Yes	1,647	365	22.2%	2.00 (1.77, 2.24)	1.49 (1.32, 1.67)
	No	553,028	69,049	12.5%		
DM	Yes	88,362	12,517	14.2%	1.19 (1.16, 1.21)	1.05 (1.03, 1.08)
	No	466,313	56,897	12.2%		
OB	Yes	139,799	22,619	16.2%	1.52 (1.49, 1.54)	1.25 (1.22, 1.27)
	No	414,876	46,795	11.3%		

Discussion

Each of the pre-existing conditions defined by this analysis, Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA), Multiple Sclerosis (MS), Diabetes Mellitus (DM), and obesity (OB) showed increased odds ratios for developing PASC. Of the four, OSA had the highest adjusted odds ratio (1.66 (1.61, 1.71) def.1, 1.59 (1.53, 1.64) def.2), followed by MS (1.58 (1.41, 1.75) def.1, 1.49 (1.32, 1.67) def.2). The odds ratio for DM was small (1.06 (1.04, 1.08) def.1, 1.05 (1.03, 1.08) def.2) with obesity having a stronger association with PASC than diabetes (1.22 (1.20, 1.23) def.1, 1.25 (1.22, 1.27) def.2) in the multivariate model. The adjusted odds ratios are lower than the univariate odds ratios, however they are still associated with an increased odds of developing PASC.

While our multivariate model attempted to correct for confounding effects of obesity and other demographic features, the multivariable models presented here could be missing important predictors. Our previous work has demonstrated that glycemic control, as measured by pre-infection HbA1c levels, is an important risk factor among patients with diabetes for poor outcomes in acute infection ⁷. Future work should explore the extent to which these risk factors for PASC, such as diabetes, may be associated with the severity of the underlying comorbidity.

Limitations

The present study utilizes our pre-existing ML models for computable phenotyping of PASC, however, our models are being continuously updated as we receive more data from sites with U09.9 codes, improve our methods, and have greater opportunity for clinical validation. We furthermore note that the computable phenotypes for OSA and obesity may have imperfect sensitivity in EHR data.

Appendix

Concept codes for Diabetes Mellitus (DM).

OMOP concept ID	OMOP concept name
4338901	Traction detachment of retina due to diabetes mellitus
4221933	Coma due to malnutrition-related diabetes mellitus
35626042	Moderate nonproliferative diabetic retinopathy of left eye
35626039	Mild nonproliferative retinopathy of left eye due to diabetes mellitus
37016768	Autonomic neuropathy due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
4175440	Autonomic neuropathy due to diabetes mellitus
195771	Secondary diabetes mellitus
380096	Proliferative retinopathy due to diabetes mellitus
43531578	Chronic kidney disease due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
318712	Peripheral circulatory disorder due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
35626038	Mild nonproliferative retinopathy of right eye due to diabetes mellitus
4228112	Hypoglycemic coma due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
45770902	Ulcer of lower limb due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
4224419	Disorder of eye due to malnutrition related diabetes mellitus
443730	Disorder of nervous system due to diabetes mellitus
4191611	Lumbosacral radiculoplexus neuropathy due to diabetes mellitus
37016356	Mild nonproliferative retinopathy due to secondary diabetes mellitus
376112	Polyneuropathy due to diabetes mellitus
4255401	O/E - right eye proliferative diabetic retinopathy
37016348	Hyperglycemia due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
4327944	Malnutrition related diabetes mellitus
4193704	Type 2 diabetes mellitus without complication

4252356	O/E - left eye proliferative diabetic retinopathy
443412	Type 1 diabetes mellitus without complication
4228443	Ketoacidotic coma due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
201530	Hyperosmolar coma due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
37016350	Dermatitis due to drug induced diabetes mellitus
4234742	Diabetic neuropathy with neurologic complication
4114427	Neuropathic arthropathy due to diabetes mellitus
443733	Disorder of eye due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
4222876	Gangrene due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
43531616	Dermopathy due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
45757435	Mild nonproliferative retinopathy due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
4140466	Lumbosacral radiculoplexus neuropathy due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
4222415	Mononeuropathy due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
200687	Renal disorder due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
4225055	Mononeuropathy due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
4131908	Peripheral angiopathy due to diabetes mellitus
37017432	Polyneuropathy due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
4227210	Retinopathy due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
376114	Severe nonproliferative retinopathy due to diabetes mellitus
380097	Macular edema due to diabetes mellitus
376065	Disorder of nervous system due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
37110593	Lesion of skin due to diabetes mellitus
443732	Disorder due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
43530656	Nonproliferative retinopathy due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
35626068	Macular edema of left eye due to diabetes mellitus
443727	Diabetic ketoacidosis
37017431	Polyneuropathy due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
43531563	Neuropathic arthropathy due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
4095288	Ketoacidotic coma due to diabetes mellitus
4221495	Cataract due to diabetes mellitus type 2
443734	Ketoacidosis due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
4224254	Ketoacidotic coma due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
45757363	Hypoglycemia due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
439770	Ketoacidosis due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
45769876	Hypoglycemia due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
37016767	Autonomic neuropathy due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
192279	Disorder of kidney due to diabetes mellitus
4196141	Arthropathy due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
201826	Type 2 diabetes mellitus
377552	Moderate nonproliferative retinopathy due to diabetes mellitus
43530690	Foot ulcer due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
321822	Peripheral vascular disorder due to diabetes mellitus
4226798	Hypoglycemic coma due to diabetes mellitus
36714116	Hypoglycemic coma due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
4225656	Cataract due to diabetes mellitus type 1
443735	Coma due to diabetes mellitus
45773064	Traction detachment of retina due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
4152858	Type 1 diabetes mellitus with arthropathy
443767	Disorder of eye due to diabetes mellitus

4223303	Gangrene due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
435216	Disorder due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
443731	Renal disorder due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
442793	Complication due to diabetes mellitus
37016349	Hyperglycemia due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
4099214	Type 1 diabetes mellitus with ulcer
4008576	Diabetes mellitus without complication
45769832	Dermopathy due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
4226238	Hyperosmolar coma due to diabetes mellitus
4044391	Neuropathy due to diabetes mellitus
4174977	Retinopathy due to diabetes mellitus
4029422	Hypoglycemic event due to diabetes
4009303	Diabetic ketoacidosis without coma
4226354	Gangrene due to diabetes mellitus
376979	Cataract due to diabetes mellitus
4227657	Skin ulcer due to diabetes mellitus
40480000	Multiple complications due to diabetes mellitus
35626067	Macular edema of right eye due to diabetes mellitus
4202383	Drug-induced diabetes mellitus
4029420	Severe hyperglycemia due to diabetes mellitus
4099651	Type 2 diabetes mellitus with ulcer
201254	Type 1 diabetes mellitus
4048028	Diabetic mononeuropathy
4159742	Diabetic foot ulcer
4033942	Diabetic dermopathy
201820	Diabetes mellitus
4096671	Malnutrition-related diabetes mellitus with peripheral circulatory complications
35626043	Severe nonproliferative retinopathy of right eye due to diabetes mellitus
4224879	Disorder of nervous system due to malnutrition related diabetes mellitus
35626044	Severe nonproliferative retinopathy of left eye due to diabetes mellitus
37016358	Moderate nonproliferative retinopathy due to secondary diabetes mellitus
4143857	Lumbosacral radiculoplexus neuropathy due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
37016180	Moderate nonproliferative retinopathy due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
45770881	Moderate nonproliferative retinopathy due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
45763583	Nonproliferative diabetic retinopathy due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
4212441	O/E - right eye stable treated proliferative diabetic retinopathy
37016179	Mild nonproliferative retinopathy due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
45769830	Neuropathic arthropathy due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
4290822	Severe nonproliferative retinopathy with clinically significant macular edema due to diabetes mellitus
443729	Peripheral circulatory disorder due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
4096670	Malnutrition-related diabetes mellitus with renal complications
45769873	Traction detachment of retina due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
4096042	Malnutrition-related diabetes mellitus without complications
4099652	Multiple complications due to malnutrition related diabetes
35626041	Moderate nonproliferative diabetic retinopathy of right eye
4215961	O/E - left eye stable treated proliferative diabetic retinopathy
45770830	Macular edema and retinopathy due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
377821	Disorder of nervous system due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
378743	Mild nonproliferative retinopathy due to diabetes mellitus

45763584	Proliferative retinopathy due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
43530685	Proliferative retinopathy due to type 2 diabetes mellitus
4096041	Malnutrition-related diabetes mellitus with ketoacidosis
42538169	Disorder of eye due to type 1 diabetes mellitus
4266637	Severe nonproliferative retinopathy without macular edema due to diabetes mellitus
4029423	Hypoglycemia due to diabetes mellitus

Literature

- 1 Keenan BT, Kirchner HL, Veatch OJ, Borthwick KM, Davenport VA, Feemster JC, *et al.* Multisite validation of a simple electronic health record algorithm for identifying diagnosed obstructive sleep apnea. *J Clin Sleep Med* 2020;**16**:175–83.
- 2 Pérez CA, Zhang G-Q, Li X, Huang Y, Lincoln JA, Samudralwar RD, *et al.* COVID-19 severity and outcome in multiple sclerosis: Results of a national, registry-based, matched cohort study. *Mult Scler Relat Disord* 2021;**55**:103217.
- 3 Culpepper WJ, Marrie RA, Langer-Gould A, Wallin MT, Campbell JD, Nelson LM, *et al.* United States Multiple Sclerosis Prevalence Workgroup (MSPWG). Validation of an algorithm for identifying MS cases in administrative health claims datasets. *Neurology* 2019;**92**:e1016–28.
- 4 Xie Y, Al-Aly Z. Risks and burdens of incident diabetes in long COVID: a cohort study. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol* 2022;**10**:311–21.
- 5 Weerahandi HM, Horwitz LI, Blecker SB. Diabetes Phenotyping Using the Electronic Health Record. *J Gen Intern Med* 2020;**35**:3716–8.
- 6 Pfaff ER, Girvin AT, Bennett TD, Bhatia A, Brooks IM, Deer RR, *et al.* Who has long-COVID? A big data approach n.d. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.10.18.21265168>.
- 7 Wong R, Hall M, Vaddavalli R, Anand A, Arora N, Bramante CT, *et al.* Glycemic Control and Clinical Outcomes in U.S. Patients With COVID-19: Data From the National COVID Cohort Collaborative (N3C) Database. *Diabetes Care* 2022. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc21-2186>.